

Thiodiazines.

Part II.

Condensation of ω -Bromacetophenone with 4-Substituted Thiosemicarbazides. The Constitution of Thiosemicarbazides.

BY

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It has been shown in Part I (this *Journal*, 1924, 1, 53) that the condensation of thiosemicarbazide with ω -bromacetophenone leads to the formation of 2-amino-5-phenyl-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazine and 2-keto-4-phenyl--2 : 3-dihydro-1 : 3-thiazole hydrazone. It was suggested therein that the formation of the thiazole derivative depended on the basic character of the 4-amino group, the ratios of the yields of the isomers being a measure of the relative basicity of the two extreme amino groups of thiosemicarbazide. A similar conclusion was arrived at by Walther and Roch (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1913, ii, 87, 27) in course of their studies on the condensation of ω -bromacetophenone with substituted thiocarbazides. If this assumption be also true of substituted thiosemicarbazides the relative quantities of the thiazole derivatives obtainable would be expected to be in harmony with the degree of basic strength of the substituted amino group in position 4. It was therefore found desirable to study the condensation of a few 4-substituted thiosemicarbazides with ω -bromacetophenone from a quantitative standpoint with a view to test the hypothesis.

In this communication the condensations of ω -brom-acetophenone with methyl-, ethyl-, allyl-, phenyl-, *p*-tolyl-, *o*-tolyl-, α -naphthyl- and β -naphthyl-thiosemicarbazides are described. The ratios of the yields of thiazoles and the corresponding thiodiazine derivatives are given in the accompanying table.

Nature of substituent.	Ratio of Thiodiazine to Thiazole derivative.	Total yield.
—	1 0·2	78 per cent.
Methyl	1 . 1	95 " "
Ethyl	1 0·3*	77 " "
Allyl	1 0·0	90 " "
Phenyl	1 0·18	86 " "
<i>p</i> -Tolyl	1 0·192*	93 " "
<i>o</i> -Tolyl	1 0·8	88 " "
α -Naphthyl	1 0·38	56 " "
β -Naphthyl	1 0 0	81 " "

If the significance of these ratios be discussed, the above hypothesis will be found inadequate to cover all the facts of experiment. For instance, on the basis of the aforesaid hypothesis the yields of the thiazole derivatives obtained ought to be in the following order :

Et > Me > C₆H₅ > unsubstituted > *p*-C₆H₄ > Ph > *o*-C₆H₄ > β -C₁₀H₇ > α -C₁₀H₇ ;

whereas the yields actually obtained are in the order :

Me > *o*-C₆H₄ > α -C₁₀H₇ > Et > unsubstituted > *p*-C₆H₄ > Ph.

Clearly then the basic character of the 4-*N* atom partaking in ring-formation cannot be regarded as the sole

* These are only approximate figures.

factor in determining the relative yields of the thiazole derivatives. The author is of opinion that the relative proportions of thiodiazine and thiazole formed in the different cases depend on the relative mobility of the hydrogen atoms attached to the several *N*-atoms, but at present he has no independent method for measuring mobility. (*Cf.* Usherwood, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1923, 42, 1249).

Substituted thiosemicarbazides of the type $RNH.CS.NH.NHR'$, which can exist in the tautomeric modifications, $RNH.C(SH):N.NHR'$ (I) or $RN:C(SH).NH.NHR'$ (II), might be expected to react with ω -bromacetophenone in either of the following ways:—

Of these (VIII) and (IX) are excluded because the products are found to contain no substituted imino groups when tested by methods available for the detection of that group (Bernthsen, *Annalen*, 1878, 192, 1; *Ber.*, 1877, 10, 1238; Traumann, *Annalen*, 1888, 249, 43; Walther and Roch, *loc. cit.*).

Moreover the thiodiazines from 4-substituted thiosemicarbazides are not oxidised to cyclic azo-compounds by nitrous acid, amyl nitrite or hydrogen peroxide in glacial

acetic acid as would be expected in the case of a compound (VIII) where $R' = H$.

1-Acetyl-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide reacts with ω -bromacetophenone to yield an acetyl thiazole which on hydrolysis is converted into the thiazole obtained directly from 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide and the bromo-ketone. Also acetone-4-methylthiosemicarbazone and anisylidene-4-methylthiosemicarbazone react with the bromoketone to give the same thiazole derivatives as are obtained by the action of acetone and anisaldehyde respectively on the thiazole from the bromoketone and 1-methylthiosemicarbazide. These facts justify the author in assigning to substituted thiosemicarbazides the formula $RNH.C(SH) = N.NHR$ in preference to the tautomeric form (II).

In the previous communication it has been definitely established that thiosemicarbazide reacts in the tautomeric form $NH_2.C(SH) : N.NH_2$ and it appears from the above considerations that 4-substituted thiosemicarbazides, their 1-acetyl derivatives as well as thiosemicarbazones react in an exactly similar manner. (*Cf.* Wilson and Burns, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 870).

It will be remembered that many reactions of substituted thiosemicarbazides recorded by Freund (*Ber.*, 1890, 23, 2821; 1896, 29, 2483), Marckwald and Bott (*Ber.*, 1896, 29, 2914), Pulvermacher (*Ber.*, 1894, 27, 613), Freund and Meinecke (*Ber.*, 1896, 29, 2511) and others have been based on the form (II). But this assumption is more or less arbitrary and it is interesting to note that the alternative form (I) might as well explain the several reactions without any serious difficulty or disadvantage.

In the previous communication the methylation product of 2-amino-5-phenyl-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazine was provisionally regarded as 2-methylamino-5-phenyl-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazine. The latter compound has now been

synthesised from 4-methylthiosemicarbazide and ω -bromacetophenone and is not identical with the compound previously obtained, which in consequence is now regarded as 2-imino-3-methyl-5-phenyl-2 : 3-dihydro-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazine. The researches of Pyman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 367; *ibid.*, 3359) and of other workers also support this conclusion.

The thiodiazines are very stable well-defined substances. They form salts with acids, which, in the case of aryl substituted derivatives, readily hydrolyse in aqueous solution. The alkyl substituted amino thiodiazines are more basic. They decompose slowly when kept in aqueous solutions for a long time. The alkyl-amino thiodiazines are less stable than the aryl-amino ones. On boiling with aqueous alkali or with water slight decomposition occurs and the solution smells of very dilute alkyl or aryl isonitrile as the case may be. The isomeric thiazole hydrazones, which are difficult to separate in a pure state from the main product of reaction, are more basic and susceptible to oxidation. The replacement of alkyl groups in position 4 of the thiazole by aryl groups increases stability but decreases the reactivity of the hydrazine group towards ketones and aldehydes. When boiled with alkali they are not affected in the same way as the thiodiazines. Phenyl, *o*-tolyl and *p*-tolyl compounds produce a red or orange precipitate when treated with nitrous acid in hydrochloric acid solution. This property is absent in the α -naphthyl compound. The thiodiazines as already stated are indifferent towards this reagent. It appears that the free amino group of the hydrazine is responsible for the reaction with nitrous acid since the acetyl derivatives or the condensation products of these hydrazones with ketones and aldehydes are not affected by this reagent.

When 2-phenylamino-5-phenyl-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazine is boiled with concentrated hydrochloric acid for 3 to 5 hours, it gradually passes into the isomeric thiazole hydrazone. This change which has also been observed with *p*-tolyl- and *o*-tolyl-amino-5-phenyl-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazines no doubt occurs through the intermediate formation of a *S*-phenacylthiosemicarbazide. Analogous cases in the tetrazine series have been recorded by Bülow (*Ber.*, 1906, 39, 4106) and by Pechmann and Bauer (*Ber.*, 1909, 42, 659).

EXPERIMENTAL.

4-Phenylthiosemicarbazide and ω-Bromacetophenone : Formation of 2-Phenylamino-5-phenyl-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazine and 2-Keto-3:4-diphenyl-2 : 3-dihydro-1:3-thiazole hydrazone.

Six grams (1 mol.) of ω -bromacetophenone and 5 gms. (1 mol.) of 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide were heated together with 40 c.c. of anhydrous alcohol for 5—10 minutes on the water-bath under reflux. The solution turned dirty red. On cooling 6.5 gms. of prismatic needles melting at 191° were obtained. The mother-liquor on being concentrated gave a further yield of 2.5 gms. (m. p. 191-95°) which under the microscope appeared to consist of two varieties of crystals. The first crop consisted almost entirely of the *hydrobromide* of 2-phenylamino-5-phenyl-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazine. The second crop was dissolved in absolute alcohol in which it was not very soluble. The solution in the course of two days deposited a mixture of (i) colourless star-like aggregates and (ii) yellow prismatic plates. These were mechanically separated from each other and (ii) was recrystallised from absolute alcohol. It begins to darken at about 206° and melts completely with decomposition between 224-26°. This compound is the *hydrobromide* of

2-keto-3 : 4-diphenyl-2 : 3-dihydro-1 : 3-thiazole hydrazone and was obtained in a yield of about 13% of that required by theory.

Found : N=12.08.

Calc. for $C_{15}H_{15}N_3SBr$: N=12.07 per cent.

The hydrobromide was dissolved in a mixture of equal volumes of alcohol and water, filtered and treated with aqueous ammonia when the free base was obtained as colourless needles. It was sparingly soluble in alcohol, acetone or benzene and was recrystallised from dilute pyridine. It begins to char at about 170° and melts completely at 198° with decomposition.

Found : N=15.84

Calc. for $C_{15}H_{15}N_3S$: N = 15.73 per cent.

2-Phenylamino-5-phenyl-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazine was obtained in a similar manner from its hydrobromide. It separates from dilute pyridine in almost colourless needles melting at 175° with decomposition.

Found : N=15.78 ; S = 11.59 ; C = 67.36 ; H=5.03.

Calc. for $C_{15}H_{15}N_3S$: N=15.73 ; S=11.99 ; C=67.42 and H=4.87 per cent.

An aqueous hydrochloric acid solution of this base does not react with nitrous acid whereas the isomeric thiazole compound under the same treatment produces an orange precipitate which is very soluble in ether but almost insoluble in acids or alkalis. It melted at 195-98° with decomposition.

The acetyl derivative of the thiodiazine was prepared by boiling the latter with excess of acetic anhydride for one hour. The product was neutralised with sodium carbonate, the residual jelly-like mass was dissolved in

caustic soda, filtered and precipitated by dilute hydrochloric acid. It was repeatedly washed with cold water and dried over sulphuric acid in vacuum. The amorphous powder thus obtained is very soluble in most organic media from which it refuses to separate out in the crystalline state. It melted indefinitely above 110° .

Found: S = 10.32.

Calc. for $C_{17}H_{15}ON_3S$: S = 10.35 per cent.

1-Acetyl-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide.

Finely powdered 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide was covered with an excess of acetic anhydride. The thiosemicarbazide dissolved and immediately solidified with considerable evolution of heat. The product was washed with cold alcohol and recrystallised from hot water in colourless glistening rectangular plates melting at 173° . It is soluble in hot alcohol, glacial acetic acid, pyridine and alkali. From an alkaline solution acids precipitated the original compound in crystalline state.

Found: N = 19.99.

Calc. for $C_9H_{11}ON_3S$: N = 20.09 per cent.

1-Acetyl-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide and ω -Bromacetophenone: Formation of 2-Keto-3:4-diphenyl-2:3-dihydro-1:3-thiazole-acetylhydrazone.

Equimolecular quantities of the components were heated with absolute alcohol for two hours on the water-bath. The solution was evaporated to dryness and the semi-solid residue was thoroughly washed with ether and finally with dry acetone, when small white crystals of the hydrobromide of the above base were obtained. It was dissolved in hot pyridine and the solution was diluted

with water and a little alcohol, when colourless needles were obtained. After recrystallisation it melted at 224°.

Found : C=64.76; H=5.08.

Calc. for $C_{17}H_{16}ON_3S$: C=64.65 and H=5.05 per cent.

It is easily soluble in alcohol, pyridine and chloroform; sparingly in benzene and acetone. The crystalline substance dissolves slowly in caustic alkalis but readily in dilute acids. From the acid solution the base may be precipitated in the amorphous state by the addition of ammonia or just sufficient caustic soda required to neutralise the acid as excess of the alkali easily dissolves the freshly precipitated base.

Hydrolysis of 2-Keto-3:4-diphenyl-2:3-dihydro-1:3-thiazoleacetylhydrazone.

The acetyl derivative was boiled with an excess of dilute hydrochloric acid for 2-3 hours until an oil began to appear in the solution. It was then cooled, filtered from the small amount of oil and basified with an excess of caustic soda when a white granular precipitate gradually separated out. On crystallisation from a mixture of pyridine and alcohol it was found to melt at 197-98° with decomposition. Its hydrochloric acid solution gave with sodium nitrite an orange precipitate melting at 195-200°. It was identical in other respects with 2-keto-3:4-diphenyl-2:3-dihydro-1:3-thiazole hydrazone obtained in the condensation of ω -bromacetophenone and 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide. A mixture of the two melted at 197°.

Found : C=67.33; H=5.24.

Calc. for $C_{15}H_{13}N_3S$: C=67.42 and H=4.87 per cent.

Acetone-4-phenylthiosemicarbazone.

An acetone solution of 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide was boiled for a few minutes. On cooling and diluting with

water colourless plates of the thiosemicarbazone were obtained. After a second crystallisation from dilute acetone the melting point was found to be 128°.

Found : N = 20·21.

Calc. for $C_{10}H_{13}N_3S$: N = 20·29 per cent.

Acetone-4-phenylthiosemicarbazone and ω-Bromacetophenone.

Equimolecular quantities of the components were boiled together in absolute alcohol for 15 minutes. The solution was then evaporated to dryness and the residue was washed with acetone. The hydrobromide was dissolved in dilute alcohol, boiled with animal charcoal and treated with aqueous ammonia when 2-keto-3 : 4-diphenyl-2 : 3-dihydro-1 : 3-thiazole-isopropylidene hydrazone separated in yellow needles. It melted at 165° after two recrystallisations from dilute pyridine.

Found : C = 68·66, 68·29 ; H = 5·73, 5·68.

Calc. for $C_{18}H_{17}N_3S, \frac{1}{2}H_2O$: C = 63·32 ; H = 5·70 per cent.

*Anisylidene-4-phenylthiosemicarbazone.**

It was obtained by boiling an alcoholic solution of 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide and anisaldehyde for a few minutes. From glacial acetic acid it separates in colourless needles melting at 190-181°.

Found : N = 14·79.

Calc. for $C_{15}H_{15}ON_3S$: N = 14·74 per cent.

Anisylidene-4-phenylthiosemicarbazone and ω-Bromacetophenone : Formation of 2-Keto-3 : 4-diphenyl-2 : 3-dihydro-1 : 3-thiazole anisylidene hydrazone.

The condensation took place within a few minutes on boiling an alcoholic solution of the components in

* The condensations of free and substituted thiosemicarbazides with various types of ketone and aldehyde are in progress.

equimolecular quantities. The alcoholic solution was treated with pyridine, when the free base appeared in long colourless cottony needles. It was recrystallised from a mixture of pyridine and alcohol when it melted at 161°.

Found : N = 11·13.

Calc. for $C_{23}H_{16}ON_3S$: N = 10·91 per cent.

The corresponding *benzylidene* compound was similarly obtained from benzylidene-4-phenylthiosemicarbazone and ω -bromacetophenone. It crystallised from dilute pyridine in yellow plates melting at 191°.

Found : N = 11·99.

Calc. for $C_{22}H_{17}N_3S$: N = 11·83 per cent.

2-Keto-3 : 4-diphenyl-2 : 3-dihydro-1 : 3-thiazolehydrazone and Anisaldehyde.

An alcoholic solution of the reactants was boiled for 2 hours when the condensation product crystallised out from the cold reaction mixture in long colourless needles, and melted at 160·61° after several recrystallisations. It seemed to be identical with the synthetic product described above on the strength of a mixed melting point determination and other physical characteristics. The quantity was too small for analysis.

*4-p-Tolylthiosemicarbazide and ω -Bromacetophenone :
Formation of 4-p-Tolylamino-5-phenyl-1 : 3 : 4-
thiodiazine.*

Six gms. of ω -bromacetophenone and 5·4 gms. of the thiosemicarbazide were boiled in absolute alcohol (40° c.o.) for a few minutes. On cooling colourless

needles of the hydrobromide of the above base were obtained. These were collected, washed with acetone and recrystallised from alcohol. The greater portion of the *hydrobromide* was thus obtained in rhombohedra melting at 195°. The isomeric base could not be obtained by the fractional crystallisation of the crude hydrobromide as in the case of the phenyl derivative described before. The mother-liquor after the removal of the thiodiazine hydrobromide was evaporated to dryness and repeatedly extracted with dilute warm hydrochloric acid. The acid extract on being treated with a solution of sodium nitrite gave a crystalline orange-red precipitate which shrank at 110° and melted with decomposition at 138-39°. It resembled the product of interaction of nitrous acid with 2-keto-3:4-diphenyl-2:3-dihydro-1:3-thiazolehydrazone in general properties.

2-*p*-Tolylamino-5-phenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine hydrobromide was dissolved in hot aqueous acetone. On treating with aqueous ammonia the *base* was precipitated in the crystalline state. After several recrystallisations from acetone it was obtained in shining pale-yellow plates melting at 179°.

Found: N=15.26; C=68.16; H=5.73.

Calc. for $C_{16}H_{15}N_3S$: N=14.95; C=68.33 and H=5.34 per cent.

The *acetyl* derivative was obtained in the same way as in the case of the phenyl compound. In solubility and other physical properties it resembled the acetyl derivative of 2-phenylamino-5-phenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine. It melted indefinitely above 115°.

Found: N=12.91; S=10.04.

Calc. for $C_{18}H_{17}ON_3S$: N=13.01; S=9.91 per cent.

4-o-Tolylthiosemicarbazide and ω -Bromacetophenone:
Formation of 2-o-Tolylamino-5-phenyl-1 : 3 : 4-
thiodiazine and 2-Keto-3-o-tolyl-4-phenyl-
2 : 3-dihydro-1 : 3-thiazole hydrazone.

The condensation was carried out in the same way as in the case of the *p*-tolyl compound. The total yield of the crude hydrobromide amounted to 93-94% of the theoretical of which about 40% appeared to be due to the isomeric thiazole hydrazone. The crude hydrobromide was dissolved in absolute alcohol and left in a crystallising dish for 3-4 days by which time the greater portion of the substance crystallised out in (i) small clusters of star-like needles and (ii) colourless stout hexagonal crystals. These were mechanically separated and each variety was recrystallised from absolute alcohol. (i) Melted at about 206-08° with complete decomposition, while (ii) melted at 185° and did not decompose even at 210°. The bases were obtained in pale-yellow needles when pyridine solution of the hydrobromides was diluted with water. The base from (i) melted at 136° after several crystallisations from dilute pyridine and gave the characteristic orange-red precipitate with nitrous acid. Evidently this compound is *2-Keto-3-o-tolyl-4-phenyl-2 : 3-dihydro-1 : 3-thiazole hydrazone*.

Found: N = 15.15.

Calc. for $C_{11}H_{15}N_3S$: N = 14.95 per cent.

The thiodiazine from (ii) was repeatedly crystallised from acetone until the melting point rose to 148°. It is sparingly soluble in benzene or alcohol and almost insoluble in ether.

Found: C = 68.60; H = 5.85.

Calc. for $C_{10}H_{10}N_3S$: C = 68.33; H = 5.34 per cent.

*2-o-Tolylamino-5-phenyl-1 : 3 : 4-t hiodiazine
and Bromine.*

The action of bromine on the phenyl and *p*-tolyl compounds resulted in the formation of tarry products from which no definite compounds could be isolated. In the case of the *o*-tolyl compound, however, a *monobromo* derivative was obtained as follows: Molecular proportions of the reactants in glacial acetic acid solution were mixed in the cold. The solution was diluted with water after some time and neutralised with sodium carbonate. The white solid, which gradually appeared, was crystallised from pyridine and finally from acetone in minute crystals which melted at 155-56°.

Found: N=11.74; Br = 22.02.

Calc. for $C_{16}H_{14}N_3SBr$: N=11.67; Br=22.22 per cent.

*Allylthiosemicarbazide and ω-Bromacetophenone :
Formation of 2-Allylamino-5-phenyl-1 : 3 : 4-
thiodiazine.*

The condensation product was isolated in about 90% of the theoretical yield as the *hydrobromide*, which crystallised from alcohol in stout rectangular plates melting at 165°. The base was obtained from a cold aqueous solution of the hydrobromide by treatment with a slight excess of aqueous ammonia or dilute sodium carbonate. The greenish yellow plates, which separated out, were collected after 2 to 3 hours, washed with cold water and dried over porous porcelain. For purification a benzene solution of the base was diluted with 4-6 times its volume of petrol ether when the thiodiazine separated in long colourless needles melting at 99°.

Found: N = 18.55.

Calc. for $C_{12}H_{12}N_2S$: N=18.26 per cent.

It is very soluble in alcohol, acetone, benzene, pyridine and chloroform, less soluble in ether and sparingly in petrol ether. It seems that the isomeric base is not produced in this condensation since all attempts to isolate it as the benzylidene or anisylidene derivative from the crude hydrobromide or from the mother-liquor left after the separation of the latter have been futile.

*4- α -Naphthylthiosemicarbazide and ω -Bromacetophenone :
Formation of 2- α -Naphthylamino-5-phenyl-1 : 3 : 4-
thiodiazine and 2-Keto-3- α -naphthyl-4-phenyl-
2 : 3-dihydro-1 : 3-thiazole hydrazone.*

α -Naphthylthiosemicarbazide (2.17 gms.) and the bromoketone (2 gms.) were boiled for a few minutes with 30 c. c. of dry ethyl alcohol. On cooling the hydrobromides of the above-mentioned bases crystallised out from the reaction mixture in 56% of the theoretical yield. On recrystallisation from alcohol a mixture of two varieties of well-defined crystals was obtained: (i) colourless rectangular needles (1.75 gms.), which softened at 203° and melted at 220° with decomposition, and (ii) pale yellowish brown rhombic crystals (0.15 gm.) melting at 208° with evolution of gases. These were mechanically separated. The *thiodiazine* was obtained from (i) by treating its aqueous-alcoholic solution with ammonia. It crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles. After three crystallisations the melting point remained constant at 166-67°.

Found: N = 13.55; S = 10.08.

Calc. for $C_{19}H_{15}N_3S$: N = 13.25; S = 10.09 per cent.

The isomeric base was obtained in a similar manner from (ii). It crystallised from alcohol in pale greenish yellow needles melting at 179°.

Found: C = 71.88; H = 5.02.

Calc. for $C_{19}H_{15}N_3S$: C = 71.92; H = 4.73 per cent.

The *acetyl* derivative of the above thiodiazine, obtained by the action of acetic anhydride on the base, is a white amorphous powder which closely resembles the acetyl derivatives already described.

Found : S = 8.53.

Calc. for $C_{21}H_{17}ON_3S$: S = 8.89 per cent

2-β-Naphthylamino-5-phenyl-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazine.

It was obtained from β -naphthylthiosemicarbazide and ω -bromacetophenone by an identical method. The hydrobromide was isolated in 76% yield of that required by theory. It was dissolved in pyridine and on dilution with water the solution quickly deposited beautiful yellow plates of the base. These were thrice recrystallised from dilute pyridine in pale-yellow plates or needles which melted at 153°. No trace of the isomer could be detected.

Found : N = 13.52.

Calc. for $C_{19}H_{15}N_3S$: N = 13.25 per cent.

4-Methylthiosemicarbazide and ω-Bromacetophenone : Formation of 2-Methylamino-5-phenyl-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazine and 2-Keto-3-methyl-4-phenyl-2 : 3-dihydro-1 : 3-thiazole-isopropylidene hydrazone.

2.62 Gms. of 4-methylthiosemicarbazide and 5 gms. of the bromo-ketone were digested with 30 c.c. of dry ethyl alcohol for 15 minutes. Alcohol was then distilled off when a dark oil remained behind. It was washed with ether and was then heated with about 20 c.c. of acetone when a dirty white crystalline product was obtained. This was collected and was washed with dry acetone. It is a mixture of the hydrobromides of the above two bases.

This was dissolved in warm water, filtered and the filtrate treated with an excess of sodium carbonate solution. The yellow crystalline product which separated out, was collected after 2-3 hours, washed well with water and dried in a vacuum (5.2 gms.). It was then dissolved in hot benzene, filtered and diluted with twice its volume of petrol ether, when *2-methylamino-5-phenyl-1:3:4-thio-diazine* was obtained as cream-coloured needles (2.4 gms.), which after two recrystallisations from benzene melted at 144-45°. It is freely soluble in alcohol, pyridine or dilute acids but almost insoluble in ligroin.

Found : N=20.83 ; C=58.56 ; H=5.90.

Calc. for $C_{10}H_{11}N_3S$: N=20.49 ; C=58.53 and H=5.37 per cent.

The *isopropylidene* derivative of the isomeric base was obtained as follows : The benzene-ligroin mother-liquor was evaporated to dryness, the residue was pressed on porous plate to remove some adhering oil and crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol in yellow plates which melted at 92-93°. It is very soluble in most organic solvents as well as in dilute acids. The synthetic product from acetone-4-methylthiosemicarbazone and ω -bromacetophenone (*vide infra*) melted at 92.5° and a mixture of these two did not alter the melting point.

Found : N=17.17.

Calc. for $C_{13}H_{15}N_3S$; N=17.14 per cent.

2-Keto-3-methyl-4-phenyl-2:3 dihydro-1:3-thiazole-anisylidene hydrazone.

In another experiment the reaction product of 4-methyl thiosemicarbazide and ω -bromacetophenone was treated with anisaldehyde in hot alcoholic solution. On

cooling yellowish needles of the hydrobromide of the above base were obtained. An aqueous-alcoholic solution of the salt on treatment with ammonia gave bright yellow plates of the base which after several crystallisations from pyridine melted at 128° . It appeared to be identical with the synthetic product (*vide infra*). Mixed m. p. $127-28^{\circ}$.

Found : N = 13.15.

Calc. for $C_{13}H_{11}ON_3S$: N = 13.00 per cent.

Acetone-4-methylthiosemicarbazone.

It is easily obtained by boiling 4-methylthiosemicarbazide in acetone solution for a few minutes. From dilute alcohol it separates in colourless needles melting at 118° .

Found : N = 29.22.

Calc. for $C_5H_{11}N_3S$: N = 28.97 per cent.

Acetone-4-methylthiosemicarbazone and ω -Bromacetophenone : Formation of 2-Keto-3-methyl-4-phenyl-2 : 3-dihydro-1 : 3-thiazole isopropylidene hydrzone.

Equimolecular quantities of the components were boiled together for a few minutes in acetone solution. The reaction begins with evolution of much heat and colourless needles of the *hydrobromide* separate out (m. p. $208-09^{\circ}$). These were dissolved in 80% methyl alcohol, filtered and treated with an excess of aqueous ammonia. The crystalline yellow plates of the *base* after two or three recrystallisations from dilute methyl alcohol melted at 92.5° .

Found : C = 63.40 ; H = 6.14.

Calc. for $C_{13}H_{13}N_3S$: C = 63.67 and H = 6.13 per cent.

Anisylidene-4-methylthiosemicarbazone and its Condensation with ω -Bromacetophenone.

Anisylidene-4-methylthiosemicarbazone, from anisaldehyde and 4-methylthiosemicarbazide, crystallises from a mixture of pyridine and alcohol in colourless shining plates melting at 207°. Like acetone-4-methylthiosemicarbazone it possesses acid properties.

Found : N = 18.82.

Calc. for $C_{10}H_{13}ON_3S$: N = 18.83 per cent.

It was condensed with the bromo-ketone in the usual manner. The *hydrobromide* of the base decomposed and melted at 235-36°. The free *base* crystallised from pyridine in yellow shining plates, which melted at 127-28°.

4-Ethylthiosemicarbazide and ω -Bromacetophenone: Formation of 2-Ethylamino-5-phenyl-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazine and 2-Keto-3-ethyl-4-phenyl-2 : 3-dihydro-1 : 3-thiazole-isopropylidene Hydrazone (?).

The procedure was similar to that of the methyl compound. The thiodiazine crystallised from benzene or dilute alcohol in colourless needles melting at 158°. It is very soluble in pyridine, less soluble in alcohol or acetone and almost insoluble in petrolether. Yield 2.7 gms. from 2.38 gms. of 4-ethylthiosemicarbazide.

Found : N = 19.24 ; C = 60.30 ; H = 6.04.

Calc. for $C_{11}H_{13}N_3S$: N = 19.18 ; C = 60.29 and H = 5.93 per cent.

The reddish brown mother-liquor (benzene), after the separation of the thiodiazine, was evaporated to dryness when a red oil was obtained. It was dissolved in dilute

methyl alcohol and treated with dilute hydrochloric acid. The clear acid solution when treated with ammonia gave a small quantity of a brown oil which gradually solidified and was probably the acetone condensation product of the isomer (.8 gm.). It could not be sufficiently purified for analysis.

The Action of Concentrated Hydrochloric Acid on 2-Phenyl- (-p-Tolyl- or -o-Tolyl)-amino-5-phenyl-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazine.

The thiodiazine was boiled with concentrated hydrochloric acid for 3 to 5 hours. The solution was cooled, filtered from a heavy oil which had formed and treated with an excess of caustic soda. A white precipitate gradually made its appearance. On crystallisation from pyridine it melted at 197° with decomposition. It gave the characteristic orange precipitate with nitrous acid and its identity with 2-keto-3 : 4-diphenyl-2 : 3-dihydro-1 : 3-thiazole hydrazone was further established by a mixed melting point determination. Similar results were obtained with *p*- and *o*-tolyl derivatives.

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